

Title:

Super Additive: Advancing Health Forecasting with Cumulative Effects of Extreme Heat, Humidity, and Air Pollution in the Lower 9th Ward Neighborhood of New Orleans

Project Summary:

Urban heat islands pose a major threat to residents, where extremely high temperatures increase the risk of both acute and chronic health impacts. Furthermore, the effects of volatile organic compounds (VOCs), which are disproportionately abundant in underserved communities, are exacerbated during periods of extreme heat, increasing the production of Ozone. This is a particularly serious concern in Southeast Louisiana, a region that includes three of country's most vulnerable heat islands along with high humidity and a concentration of petroleum refining, industrial agriculture, and chemical production activities. Dangerous temperature warnings are frequently issued during the summer months, and the state also provides air quality indicators at the parish level. However, regional indicators are insufficient to capture the exceptional conditions in urban heat islands, where the combined effects of temperature, humidity, and pollutants are far more hazardous than for surrounding areas.

Air pollution estimates from Earth-observing satellite-based sensors are, at this moment, achieving breakthroughs in monitoring capability at neighborhood-level scale, reporting at sufficient frequency to enable the estimation of potential risks through the day. The recently launched TEMPO (Tropospheric Emissions: Monitoring of Pollution) sensor represents a significant advancement by providing hourly measurements of key pollutants like ozone, nitrogen dioxide, and formaldehyde across North America with unprecedented spatial detail. Ground truth sensors from the established PANDORA and AERONET systems, as well as networks of community-managed air and temperature sensors, can validate and support further downscaling of pollution estimates to the census block and block-to-block level, as well as calibrate particulate matter estimations. These sources provide a rich data stream, with the potential to enable the generation of precise, localized health risk forecasts that are specifically tailored to the unique environmental and infrastructure conditions of local communities. The development of such a forecasting tool is the objective of this project, which unites an experienced, multidisciplinary team to develop predictive models for health risk to support local communities in the city of New Orleans. The Super Additive project leverages high-resolution Earth observation data, which will be locally validated and downscaled using advanced ground-based instruments from the PANDORA spectrometer system and AERONET (Aerosol Robotic Network), alongside an extensive network of air and temperature sensors strategically deployed throughout the community. The integration of these data sources will enable the generation of precise, localized health risk forecasts.

Super Additive will be developed in partnership with the Sankofa Community Development Corporation (Sankofa-CDC), an organization that strategically integrates health, justice, and community strengthening engagements to advance wellbeing and community resilience in the Lower Ninth Ward of New Orleans. The Lower Ninth Ward is a historically significant, underserved, and environmentally vulnerable area of New Orleans that was particularly devastated by Hurricane Katrina in 2005. Sankofa-CDC has initiated a Resilience Hub in a 40-acre wetland park to provide a

haven during extreme weather events, and health risk forecasting provided by Super Additive will enable the timely and efficient utilization of this resource to assist at-risk community members. Additionally, Super Additive health risk application will aid in the development of mitigation programs and contribute to evidence-based community advocacy efforts to improve environmental conditions in the Lower Ninth Ward, serving as a model for other heat island communities throughout the state of Louisiana.